

To Study the Effect of Castes on Marital Adjustment of Working and Non-Working Women of Ranikhet, State Of Uttarakhand

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to investigation the effect between working women belonging to scheduled caste and non working women belonging to scheduled caste, other backward caste and general caste. The result shows that there is exists a significant effect of working condition women on marital adjustment. But on the other hand the simple effects of castes were significant at any level of confidence. Further the interaction effect between working condition of women and caste was also not found significant at any level of confidence.

Key words:- Respondent, working and non-working women, caste, working condition, level of significant.

Introduction: - In married life, the interpersonal and the interaction that are marital adjustment. The marriage partners and other members of the family might have to establish harmonious relationship amongst themselves as well as individually with themselves in order to achieve marital adjustment (Hallaman, 1963). The problem of women employment has attracted the attention of many psychologists and sociologist in the united state of studies on married women in the book “employed mothers in American”. On the other hand, some exploratory studies have shown an interaction between employment and marital adjustment (Vijay Laxmi, 1997). The effect of women employment and marital adjustment .A sample of 100 working and 100 non-working women, age group 20-40 years completed a marital adjustment questionnaire. Findings reveal that marital adjustment was inferable influenced by the employment status working and non-working women (Bawa, 1996). The adjustment problem of working women, a sample 200 women, 150 working women, 50 non working women between 25-50 years .result reveal that non working women had better marital adjustment then working women and non-working women obtained a significant higher scores on marital adjustment than working women(Neeta,2001).

There are a lot of differences among women of the three groups of caste with respect to education and socio-economic status. Consequesquently, the women of scheduled caste are many problems and difficulties in their marital life in comparison to other backward caste and general caste (Durodoys, 1997).The effect of religion on marital stability that the hetrogamy in religion affected marital stability (Adelmann, 1997). Some researcher found that there is no interaction between caste and marital adjustment.

Objectives under study:-

1. To study the effect caste of marital adjustment working women.
2. To study the effect of marital adjustment no working women.

Null research Hypotheses:-

1. There is no significant effect of caste on marital adjustment.
2. There is no significant effect of working condition of women on marital adjustment.
3. There is no significant interaction between caste and working condition of women on marital adjustment.

Research methodology:-

Area of Study:-

This Place is in the border of the Almora District Ranikhet, which means *Queen's meadow* in Hindi, gets its name from a local legend, which states that it was here, that Raja Sudhardev won the heart of his queen, Rani Padmini, who subsequently chose the area for her residence, giving it the name, Ranikhet .The small and deliberately undeveloped hill station of Ranikhet, 50 km West of Almora, is essentially an army cantonment, the home of the Kumauni Rifles. New construction is confined to the. Sadar Bazaar area, while the rest of the town above it, climbing up towards the crest of the

hill, retains atmospheric leafy pine woods. Beautiful forest trails abound, including short cuts from the bazaar to the Mall; leopards still roam some of the more remote areas within the town boundaries, despite efforts by army officers to prove their hunting skills. Study was conducted in four Village rural areas of tehsil Ranikhet district Almora. Distribution of the area of research was consisted a number of villages from rural areas of the tehsil Ranikhet, which were randomly selected. All of village was selected to capture maximum variation in data.

Study design:-

In this paper the design is a randomized group design whose elements have been selected on the bases of randomization working and non-working women belonging to the different caste selected total number 90 respondent. The study proceeds with 2x3 factorial designs.

Sample size

The question about the sample size is often asked that how much it has to be large. The answer depends on various aspects such as population size, population characteristics, time, available resources, and kind of data analysis to select a representative sample size. It is not necessary that a large sample size would be a true representative sample. Cross-sectional study was conducted to examine the effect of socio-economic and demographic characteristics of the respondents. In which 45 working and 45 non working women were selected 30 respondents related to scheduled caste, 30 were related to other backward caste and 30 respondents related to general caste. Respondents, who were related to working condition different areas.

Data collection

Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used to get meaningful and detailed information. Information was collected using a questionnaire consisting on both open and closed ended questions relevant to research objectives. Before starting actual data collection activity pre-testing on 15 respondents was carried out to examine the workability and sensitivity of the questionnaire.

The analysis and interpretation of data:-The analysis of data was carried out by applying the statistical methods of 2x3 factorial designs and two way ANOVA table and calculate the variance.

Table 1. The caste wise working condition of women (2x3 factorial designs)

Caste	Working condition of women	
	Scheduled caste	15
Other backward caste	15	15
General caste	15	15

The marital adjustment inventory was administered on 90 respondents according to the instruction given in the test manual. The test has to be administered in the group, situation as well as at the individual level. Respondents, who were related to working condition the test has to be administered at the group situation. On the other hand when the respondents were non-working condition the test has to be administered at the individual level.

Table 2. The mean of working women and non-working women.

Caste	Working condition of women		Non-working condition of women	
	Total	Mean	Total	Mean
Scheduled caste	267	17.8	307	20.4
Other backward caste	287	19.1	297	19.8
General caste	285	19.0	310	20.6

Table3. The Analysis of variance

Variance	SS	DF	MS	F-value
Working condition of women	69.49	1	69.45	13.11**
Caste(B)	7.35	2	3.67	.69
AxB	15.00	2	7.5	1.41
With in treatment error	445.62	84	5.3	

****Significance at .01%level of confidence**

Result:-The result by ANOVA table can be enumerated under given-

1. The simple effect of working condition of women is found significant at .01% level of confidence.
2. The simple effect of caste is not found significant at .01% level of confidence
3. The interaction effect between working condition of women and caste is also not found significant at .01% level of confidence.

Conclusion: - The present study aimed to see the marital adjustment between the working women belonging to the scheduled caste, other backward caste and general caste and the non-working women belonging to the scheduled caste, other backward caste and general caste also. On the bases of ANOVA Table, we can say that the three hypotheses formulated. “There is no significant effect of working condition of women on marital adjustment”, proved wrong because they obtained F-value 13.11 is larger than the critical value 6.96 at .01% level of confidence. On the bases of F-value we can prove that there is significant difference between working women and non-working women on marital working women had better marital adjustment than working women. To conclude, the effect of working condition of women and caste can be measure on marital adjustment.

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